

Studies on Nitrofuranyl Heterocycles. Part-II. Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of 2-Aryl-4-(5-nitro-2-furyl)thiazoles

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Manuscript received 22 September 1986, accepted 10 July 1987

The preparation of fourteen new 2-aryl-4-(5-nitro-2-furyl)thiazoles is described. These compounds are evaluated for antibacterial activity against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. The results of the screening indicate that the title compounds carrying *o*-chloro, *o*-hydroxy, *p*-nitro and dimethoxy substituents in the aryl moiety possess excellent antibacterial activity against all the organisms tested.

VARIOUS thiazole derivatives have been found to be associated with diverse pharmacological activities, such as antibiotic, antiinflammatory, schistosomicidal and fungicidal properties¹. During the course of their investigations on 5-nitrofuranyl antibacterials which did not contain an azine system ($-C=N-N-C-$), Sherman and Dickson² reported a series of 2-amino-4-(5-nitro-2-furyl)thiazole derivatives and observed that the above compounds exhibited antibacterial activity *in vitro*, particularly against *S. aureus*, *Salmonella* and *E. coli*. Subsequently, a number of papers and patents have described the preparation and antibacterial properties of a variety of nitrofuranylthiazoles³⁻⁹. However, no work is reported on the synthesis of 2-aryl-4-(5-nitro-2-furyl)thiazoles.

In continuation of our work on nitrofuranyl derivatives of biological interest^{10,11}, we present in this paper, the synthesis and biological activity of hitherto unknown 4-(5-nitro-2-furyl)thiazoles (3), carrying aryl substituents in the thiazole ring. During the present work, the nitrofuranylthiazoles (3) were synthesised according to the method of Hantzsch *et al.*¹² by condensing various substituted arene-thiocarboxamides (1) with 2-bromoacetyl-5-nitrofuranyl (2) (Scheme 1). The arene-thiocarboxamides (1) were obtained by passing hydrogen

sulphide to an alcoholic solution of the corresponding aromatic nitriles in presence of triethanolamine. The aromatic nitriles, in turn, were prepared from the respective aldehydes employing the procedure of Van Es¹³. 2-Bromoacetyl-5-nitro-furan (2) was obtained by the bromination of 5-nitro-2-acetyl-furan⁶. The arene-thiocarboxamides (1) when condensed with 2-bromoacetyl-5-nitrofuranyl (2) in the presence of aqueous sodium acetate in alcohol medium, gave the title compounds (3) in 60–90% yields. As a part of structure-activity studies, various substituents like chloro, hydroxy, nitro, methoxy, methylenedioxy *etc.*, were incorporated into the aryl moiety of these thiazoles. Compounds 3m and 3n carrying benzyl and *p*-chlorobenzyl substituents instead of aryl substituent at position-2 of the thiazole ring, were also synthesised (Table 1).

The structures of the newly synthesised compounds (3) were confirmed by elemental analyses, ir and nmr spectral data. Characteristic ir absorption bands of the carbonyl moiety of the starting material (2) and the NH absorption bands of the arene-thiocarboxamides (1) were absent in the spectra of the condensed products (3).

Nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of 3a is fully consistent with the assigned structure. A sharp singlet integrating for one proton, observed at δ 7.8, is attributed to the thiazole 5-H¹⁴. The signal due to 3-H of the nitrofuranyl ring appeared as a doublet at δ 7.02 (*J* 3.5Hz) similar to the observations made by Sasaki and Yoshioka¹⁵, while the doublet of the 4-H of the nitrofuranyl ring was found mingled with the signal due to aromatic protons of the phenyl ring and appeared as a multiplet at δ 7.35–7.55 integrating for six protons. The pmr spectrum of 3d was consistent with the thiazole structure. A doublet (*J* 3.5 Hz) at δ 6.75 and a singlet at 7.6 were observed for

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) NH₂OH, HCl, HCO₂H, HCO₂Na, Δ , (ii) H₂S/EtOH, N(OH,OH)₂, (iii) NaOAc/EtOH.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-4-(5-NITRO-2-FURYL)THIAZOLE (3)

Compd. no.	R	Yield %	M p.* °C	Colour crystal form	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						O	H	N
3a	Phenyl	80	181-2 ^d	Yellow (stout cube)	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₂ SO ₂	57.70 (57.35)	2.73 (2.94)	10.18 (10.29)
3b	2-Methylphenyl	66	118 ^a	Pale yellow (crystal)	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ SO ₂	58.91 (58.74)	3.54 (3.49)	9.61 (9.79)
3c	4-Methylphenyl	90	169-71 ^c	Yellow (flake)	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ SO ₂	58.80 (58.74)	3.25 (3.49)	9.71 (9.79)
3d	2-Chlorophenyl	85	185-7 ^d	Yellow (needle)	C ₁₁ H ₇ ClN ₂ SO ₂	51.00 (50.90)	2.84 (2.28)	9.28 (9.13)
3e	4-Chlorophenyl	90	171-2 ^b	Green (crystal)	C ₁₁ H ₇ ClN ₂ SO ₂	50.70 (50.90)	2.45 (2.28)	9.32 (9.13)
3f	3,4-Methylene-dioxyphenyl	79	271-2 ^a	Yellow (needle)	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₂ SO ₂	59.00 (59.16)	2.73 (2.53)	9.08 (8.86)
3g	4-Methoxyphenyl	92	221-3 ^d	Yellow (needle)	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ SO ₂	56.00 (55.63)	3.15 (3.31)	9.11 (9.27)
3h	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	84	167-8 ^d	Yellow (cube)	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ SO ₂	54.60 (54.21)	3.68 (3.61)	8.21 (8.43)
3i	2-Hydroxyphenyl	85	175-6 ^d	Yellow (crystal)	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₂ SO ₂	54.28 (54.16)	2.68 (2.77)	9.61 (9.72)
3j	3-Nitrophenyl	68	117-8 ^c	Yellow (needle)	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₃ SO ₂	49.00 (49.21)	2.16 (2.20)	13.41 (13.24)
3k	4-Nitrophenyl	75	204-5 ^b	Red (needle)	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₃ SO ₂	49.40 (49.21)	2.36 (2.20)	13.06 (13.24)
3l	N,N-Dimethylaminophenyl	60	168-70 ^c	Orange (flake)	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ SO ₂	57.51 (57.14)	4.04 (4.12)	13.14 (13.33)
3m	Benzyl	69	122-8 ^c	Yellow (needle)	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ SO ₂	59.00 (58.74)	3.21 (3.49)	9.61 (9.79)
3n	4-Chlorobenzyl	62	104 ^c	Yellow (needle)	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₂ SO ₂	52.20 (52.42)	2.76 (2.80)	8.94 (8.79)

* Solvent of crystallisation : ^aDMF, ^bAcOH, ^cEtOH, ^dbenzene, ^edioxane.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF 2-ARYL-4-(5-NITRO-2-FURYL)THIAZOLES (3)

Compd. no.	Minimum inhibitory concentration μ g/disk* (diameter of zone of inhibition, mm)			
	<i>B. s</i>	<i>S. au</i>	<i>A. ae</i>	<i>E. s</i>
3a	<5 (12.8)	50 (13.1)	<5 (11.5)	<5 (10.9)
3b	15 (9.5)	50 (9.9)	15 (10.7)	15 (11.4)
3c	5 (11.1)	40 (10.8)	5 (8.7)	<5 (11.0)
3d	<5 (13.8)	<5 (10.1)	<5 (11.7)	<5 (15.0)
3e	5 (10.5)	5 (11.6)	5 (8.3)	10 (8.6)
3f	15 (8.1)	30 (9.8)	70 (12.1)	20 (9.0)
3g	10 (11.4)	40 (9.1)	15 (8.6)	10 (10.9)
3h	<5 (18.6)	<5 (9.9)	<5 (18.1)	<5 (16.4)
3i	<5 (18.4)	<5 (8.6)	<5 (19.4)	<5 (17.9)
3j	5 (9.9)	20 (12.3)	5 (10.1)	5 (9.8)
3k	<5 (23.9)	5 (7.0)	<5 (24.3)	<5 (23.4)
3l	5 (11.7)	10 (7.2)	5 (12.0)	<5 (13.2)
3m	5 (13.2)	<5 (7.1)	<5 (15.3)	<5 (12.8)
3n	<5 (15.2)	<5 (9.3)	<5 (12.9)	<5 (20.3)
Furacin	<5 (12.65)	<10 (14.45)	<5 (10.20)	<5 (11.15)

* Minimum inhibitory concentration is the lowest concentration of the compound that prevents visible growth after 24 h of incubation. *B. s* = *Bacillus subtilis*, *S. au* = *Staphylococcus aureus*, *A. ae* = *Aerobacter aerogenes*, *E. s* = *Escherichia coli*.

the nitrofuran 3-H and thiazole 5-H, respectively. The signal due to the *ortho*-proton of the aryl moiety appeared as a multiplet at δ 7.95 integrating for one proton. The signals due to the remaining aromatic protons and nitrofuran 4-H were again found mingled and appeared as a multiplet centered at δ 7.1 integrating for five protons.

The nitrofurlythiazoles (3a-n) thus synthesised, were subjected to antibacterial screening, against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria employing the disc-diffusion technique¹⁸ and the results are given in Table 2.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. 2-Bromoacetyl-5-nitrofurane (2) was obtained by nitration and subsequent bromination of 2-acetylfuran. The arene-thiocarboxamides (1) were obtained from the corresponding nitriles by passing hydrogen sulphide in presence of triethanolamine in alcohol medium.

General method of synthesis of 2-substituted-4-(5-nitro-2-furyl)thiazoles: An equimolecular mixture of arene-thiocarboxamides (1; 0.01 mol) and 2-bromoacetyl-5-nitrofurane (2; 0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 1-2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and neutralised with aqueous 10% (w/v) sodium acetate solution. The yellow precipitate, thus obtained was collected by filtration, washed

with water and recrystallised from a suitable solvent to yield the title compounds (3).

Evaluation of antibacterial activity of 2-substituted-4-(5-nitro-2-furyl)thiazoles (3) : Antibacterial activities of the title compounds (3a-n) were determined by the disc-diffusion method as described by us in our previous publication¹¹. Nitrofurazone¹⁷ was used as standard drug and solvent control was kept. The results of antibacterial testing are given in Table 2.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. M. R. Gajendragad, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Mangalore University, for his interest and Dr. K. R. Sridhar, Department of Bio-Sciences, for antibacterial testing. The authors are also thankful to Head, R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow and Head, R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Madras, for providing the elemental analyses and nmr spectra, respectively. One of the authors (B.K.) is grateful to Mangalore University for a Research Fellowship.

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